

Samuel Forde, Cork's 'Young Raphael', in Castlehaven Church

By Finola Finlay

In 1827, in a sustained burst of creativity over the course of two days, a brilliant young artist produced three paintings for St Patrick's Cathedral in Skibbereen. That artist was Samuel Forde, 'Cork's Young Raphael.' He was to die tragically a few months later and the paintings he created for the Cathedral now hang in St Barrahanes Catholic Church, Castlehaven (Fig 1).

How did the paintings end up in Castlehaven, when they were created for Skibbereen? The Cathedral underwent extensive re-modelling in the 1840s and again in 1881-1883¹. During the latter period a semi-circular apse was built to accommodate the altar, with stained glass windows behind it. If the paintings were hanging behind the altar, as seems likely, they were moved to accommodate the 1880s changes. It is possible that the paintings were not hanging behind the altar, but on a side wall, in which case the date of 1840s would be correct since this was when the side galleries were added. In either case, the Castlehaven church was already there to receive the paintings - it appears on the 1840s Ordnance Survey map as 'R.C. Chapel.' Lewis, in his Topographical Directory, describes it as "a large and commodious edifice, erected by subscription in 1834, on the lands of Raheens, about a mile from Castle Townsend."² This church also underwent remodelling and improvements in 1883, and the subsequent ceremonies, of its dedication to St Barrahanes, were reported in full in the *Eagle* and *County Cork Advertiser* for Saturday October 6th of that year. Curiously, while many aspects of the newly-refurbished church are described and praised, there is no mention of the paintings, leading me to wonder if they arrived after October of 1883.

Whichever it was, the paintings, which are now almost 200 years old, have been in Castlehaven Church, high on the west wall, for at least 140 years.

Incredibly, these three works are the only finished paintings we know of by Samuel Forde, apart from a self-portrait. Most of his other extant works consist of sketches, studies for his masterwork, *Fall of the Rebel Angels*, a monochrome 'bodycolour' (a type of watercolour) and his great

but unfinished *Fall*. We know he painted theatre sets and also ceilings, but none has survived. The triptych was commissioned by the church in Skibbereen, who asked another painter to do it. But that painter was more comfortable with miniatures, so passed on the commission to Forde, who produced it in one burst of energy, using the skills he had acquired as a theatrical set painter working with distemper.

Forde kept a diary, which was broken up after he died. Some of it came into the possession of J.F Maguire and some was used for an anonymous biographical sketch in the *Dublin University Magazine* of 1845. Maguire incorporated portions of the diary into his 1853 *The Industrial Movement in Ireland*³. Here is the relevant entry for the Castlehaven paintings:

November 1827 Painted Crucifixion for Skibbereen, from two o'clock, November 8, to half-past two o'clock, November 10. Painted in light and shadow, glazed with Sienna and Lake. November 12. Settled once more in Cork.

Fig 1: The three Forde Paintings on the west wall of Castlehaven Church. Photograph by Finola Finlay.

It is possible that Forde had started, or even largely completed, these canvases in his Cork studio, and was describing the process of finishing and glazing them in Skibbereen.

From those diaries and from the research of Michael Waldron and Shane Lordan⁴, we know a little about Samuel Forde (Fig 2). He was part of the golden circle that included Daniel Maclise and John Hogan, early students in what became the Cork (later Crawford) School of Art. Recognised by his classmates for his rare talent, he was supported financially by his older brother, a noted musician, after the father had abandoned his family. This allowed him to attend school where he learned several languages. He was also an autodidact, learning Greek on his own, copying from prints, and reading Shakespeare. At the age of thirteen he was one of the first students to enrol in the new Cork School of Art, the core of which was the Canova Casts, which still dominate the first floor of what is now the Crawford Gallery. The Canova collection's "strictly Greco-Roman style had a marked influence on much of Forde's early work, which displays his love for form and expression as well as his great ability to portray both."⁵

Fig 2: Samuel Forde, Portrait of the Artist (Self-Portrait), c.1828. Collection Crawford Art Gallery, Cork.

Forde's genius was recognised by everyone and he began to teach at the School at sixteen. He supported himself also by painting theatrical sets - a practice that ensured he could work quickly and on a large scale. He was in demand for painting friezes and ceilings in private houses, business premises and theatres, but unfortunately examples have not survived. What did survive of these large-scale works was a cartoon or study for *A Vision of Tragedy*, now in the Victoria and Albert Museum.⁶

After his completion of the Skibbereen commission in November 1827 Forde began his monumental work, *Fall of the Rebel Angels*. This is a work "entirely of the artist's own vision, making it an exemplar of his creative genius free from the limitations or demands of commissioned work. Several highly finished figure studies attest to the level of detail he conceived for it, and the painting attracted much attention from the start, with several of Cork's leading citizens calling on Forde to see it."⁷

But Forde was already gravely ill and unable to complete his master-

piece. Nevertheless, unfinished as it is, it now takes pride of place in the Canova Room of the Crawford Gallery, having been discovered folded up in storage. Forde died, aged only 23, on July 29th, 1828.⁸

The central scene of the three paintings is the Crucifixion, flanked by Mary on the left (originally identified as St Brigid) and Patrick on the right (Fig 3).

The Crucifixion is assured and emotive, depicting Christ on the cross with the Three Marys - his mother, her sister Mary the wife of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene. This grouping is based on John 19:25: *Now there stood by the cross of Jesus His mother, and His mother's sister, Mary of Clopas, and Mary Magdalene.*

The Virgin Mary has collapsed into the arms of her sister, while Mary Magdalene weeps at Jesus's feet. Mary Magdalene is shown as bare-shouldered with long hair, whereas the other two women wear full robes and hair coverings.

We know that Forde used to visit Carey's Lane Chapel (now replaced

Fig 3: Crucifixion. Photograph by Finola Finlay.

Fig 4: Crucifixion by Tintoretto (Wikimedia Commons).

by Sts Peter and Paul Church) "to view its fine copy of Guido Reni's Crucifixion"⁹ The influence of Reni is readily apparent in the crucified figure and in the posture of Mary Magdalene, as she crouches, grasping the cross, with long hair falling over her shoulders (although that depiction of Mary Magdalene was relatively common in Renaissance art). In the Reni, on either side of the crucifix stand Mary and John, whereas John is absent from Forde's Crucifixion.

Another source of inspiration may have been a Crucifixion by Tintoretto¹⁰ (Fig 4). In this version (Tintoretto did more than one), Mary the Mother of Jesus is being supported by her sister, Mary the wife of Clopas. To the right is a bearded, elderly, and strikingly apparelled figure in a turban and long red robe. In Forde's composition, the turbaned man is likely a representation of Joseph of Arimathea. In his long red robe, this figure introduces a conspicuous note of colour into the overall composition.

The painting on the left shows Mary, the mother of Jesus, clothed exactly as she is in the crucifixion scene, but standing, with a crescent moon and a snake under her feet (Fig 5). The snake represents evil and is a common element of Marian imagery. Her eyes are cast upwards, her face a model of pious resignation. The moon is from Revelations 12:1 - *And there appeared a great wonder in heaven; a woman clothed with the sun, and the moon under her feet, and upon her head a crown of twelve stars.* Verses 12:7 to 12:9 in *Revelation* describes the fall of the angels - a subject that was to occupy Forde as he worked on his great unfinished canvas.

St Patrick is shown in rich episcopal robes, holding his crozier in his left hand while his right hand is raised in a gesture of blessing. He is wearing a bejewelled bishop's mitre and his gaze is directed upwards. A snake scurries away at his feet. While St Patrick may seem a curious choice for this triptych, the Skibbereen Cathedral was dedicated to St Patrick, which probably accounts

Fig 5: Mary. Photograph by Finola Finlay.

for the inclusion.

Close examination of the canvas reveals that the Mary and Patrick paintings were intended to be framed as ovals, rather than rectangular. They were, apparently, conserved in the 1970s but may need some attention again.

If Samuel Forde had lived there is no doubt his career would have been as illustrious as that of his contemporaries Maclise and Hogan. It is possible that more of his works will turn up over time, but meanwhile, we can only marvel that in quiet Castlehaven, by a series of circumstances, there exists such a testament to the Young Raphael of Cork.

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REFERENCES

1. St Patrick's Cathedral Brochure, published by Skibbereen Catholic Parish of the Diocese of Cork and Ross, 2017
2. Lewis, Samuel. *A topographical Dictionary of Ireland*. Volume 1. London: S. Lewis & Co., 1837.
3. This information and all subsequent biographical details are from *Samuel Forde: Visions of Tragedy*, the Catalogue that accompanied the exhibition of that name at the Crawford Gallery in Cork in 2014, published by The Crawford Gallery. The Exhibition was curated by Michael Waldron and Shane Lordan, who also wrote the catalogue text, along with Peter Murray. Cited from now on as *Catalogue*.
4. Besides the Catalogue, Michael Waldron and Shane Lordan also wrote a piece for the Irish Arts Review, winter issue (November 2013 – February 2014), titled *A Vision of Tragedy*.
5. Catalogue, p 9
6. *A Vision of Tragedy* can be viewed online at <https://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O113973/a-vision-of-tragedy-bodycolour-samuel-forde/>.
7. Catalogue, p 14
8. Two obituaries for Forde are recorded in Michael Waldron and Shane Lordan's blog, *The Samuel Forde Project: rediscovering an artistic genius*, available at <https://samuelforde.wordpress.com/>. The post containing the obits is dated, fittingly, July 29, 2014. The blog is engagingly written and illustrated and contains much information about Forde and the process of rediscovering him.
9. Catalogue p 11. Reni's Crucifixion may be viewed at <https://gallerix.org/storeroom/92756855/N/8424/>
10. Crucifixion by Jacopo Tintoretto, Civic Museum of Padua. In the Public Domain.